

PROTOCOL TO CARRY OUT FOCUS GROUP ACTIVITIES

TARGET GROUP: YOUNG POPULATIONS

Background

The present document constitutes the protocol to be followed when carrying out focus group activities with youngsters within the framework of climate-change adaptation processes. The focus group is framed within a set of activities with stakeholders to empower and engage citizens in the co-design and co-production processes, which have as an overarching objective to establish plans and strategies to help cities, metropolitan areas and/or regions to adapt to climate change risks that may impact that geographical area.

This is a core part of the activities developed within the Horizon Europe AGORA project which supports the analysis of methodological tools for citizen-engagement and has tested diverse approaches that may be applicable in diverse settings. This protocol has been implemented with the specific target group in four diverse socio-economic frameworks, namely the metropolitan city of Rome, Italy; the city of Zaragoza and Community of Aragón, Spain; the city of Malmö, Sweden and the city of Dresden, Germany.

The type of climate risks each geographical area is exposed to is different, the sociodemographic reality is also unique. By testing the protocol in diverse frameworks, the methodology it can be confirmed the reproducibility and validity of the processes involved. In the following sections, each of the steps of the protocol are outlined for the in-person focus group sessions. They begin with an introductory session which includes the arrival/registration, consent, background and objective of the focus group, and then the methodologies implemented. In the next sections of this protocol, the outline and content will be explained, taking as an example the implementation in the Focus Group carried out within the Adaptation AGORA project in the Rome Pilot.

Implementation of the methodology

Focus groups can provide valuable insights and allow for individuals to express their views without specific limitations when compared to the implementation of other types of methodologies. It is recommended to have at hand pens and paper to allow participants to write down their ideas and thoughts during the different activities.

Location and challenges of face-to-face meetings

Focus group method requires the identification of individuals and their personal views, data protection becomes a key factor. Ensuring the face-to-face event will be carried out in a location that allows for the meeting to be developed in private, that all participants are respectful and aware of each other's privacy is crucial. Because of this, selecting an adequate venue, having an enclosed space dedicated to the meeting during a specific timeframe, without interruptions, is the first step to carry out this workshop. Making sure participants are knowledgeable of the location is also highly important, particularly in large metropolitan areas such as the city of Rome, where there are large distances.

When choosing the physical space, it is also important to consider the implications that it may have for specific groups of people. Considering youngsters as a target audience, it is important that the background of these individuals and their personal-professional situation is taken into consideration. Many young adults balance work and studies, hence their schedule may be complicated, and the location can significantly impact the potential participation in such face-to-face events.

In this context, if the focus group is organized by an independent research organization linked to a university where it is known that many members of this cohort attend, carrying it out within the premises of this institution can be a good alternative. Other options may include coworking spaces, areas within geographical connection hubs such as a Train Station (like in the case of Rome the train station Stazione Tiburtina which hosts an innovation lab), or independent organizations which may not be related to the subjects' studies but other activities, as it could be the case of volunteering.

It can be evaluated whether translations into other languages are necessary, given that youngsters living in certain areas may come from other regions and/or countries, not yet being familiar with the local language. This will be depending on the level of domain that participants have of the vehicular and/or official language spoken in the city/region where the event is taking place. This applies also to the potential need of interpreters or

translators, which should be addressed prior to the day of the event. When sharing the information and selecting the participants, which will depend on the scope and objective of the research, this factor would be taken into consideration. This may also determine the location, depending on these language needs.

In the case of the AGORA Rome Pilot activities, the World Wildlife Foundation Italy premises were deemed adequate for the focus group face-to-face encounters, as it has a central location, it is an independent institution supporting the conservation of wildlife and individuals participating would feel welcome as well as it being geographically accessible.

LOCATION: WWF Italia ETS, Via Po, 25/c, 00198 Rome RM

In this context, as individuals arrive, it is important that they feel well-received and a good environment is created. For most youngsters, a welcome coffee with some snacks can be recommended, or refreshment beverages and snacks. The combination of food and drink should be present independent of the timing when the event takes place. It is important to consider potential limitations and adequacy of the product offering, considering the audience.

For instance, it is important to consider potential food restrictions participants may have, such as intolerances, allergies, religious or personal choices. Particularly younger audiences are paying more attention to locally sourced foods that are animal cruelty-free, which is also something else to be taken into consideration. Because of this, choosing alternatives that can be a good fit-for-all such as gluten, lactose free and vegan, can be a good mix that ensures all participants will find suitable choices and feel welcome. This can be an initial subconscious first step that will make them feel welcome and willing to participate in good spirits.

Aside from the initial welcome refreshments, it is important that participants are aware of the implications of their participation, the usage of their personal data as well as how their views will be integrated into the research. While participants arrive, the registration process should include sharing with them the necessary documents and framework, as well as signing either physically or virtually the consent form.

In the event photos will be taken before, during or after the event, it is important to specify this information in the consent document, as well as how their personal data will be treated in alignment and respect with the European GDPR. It would be positive to also take an initial photo with participants of the event (provided they have granted their

consent) as some may need to leave early or right when the focus group activity finishes and therefore may not be in the picture.

Lastly, materials to carry out the focus group may include visual or physical support with guidelines for each activity, key definitions and concepts and examples; pencils/pens, sheets of papers, canvas or pre-defined tables that participants will fill out (depending on the approach). With younger cohorts, as it will be explained in detail in each of the activities of the focus group, digital formats may be preferred, hence it would be advisable to get to know the participants in this regard beforehand.

INTRODUCTORY SESSION

Estimated time: 25-30 minutes

The introductory session will include all activities carried out from the moment individuals arrive until the first activity of the focus group takes place. It will also comprise a brief presentation on the background of the focus group activity, sharing which is the purpose, who will be taking the lead, facilitators, total duration, step-by-step processes that will be carried out, how the data will be analysed and stored and who will have access to it and for what purpose. Timing for this first phase has been estimated of a total duration of 25-30 minutes, which also allows for late-comers to be present by the time the information-sharing phase starts.

The agenda for this introductory phase has been divided into three blocks, with an estimated duration included in the description below:

- **Welcome - 10 minutes:** Initial arrival, registration (including signing consents) and refreshments. If all participants are present, during this phase it would be ideal to take a group photo.

- **Meet and greet - 10 minutes:** Participant's getting to know one another, they should be seated in a circle or semi-circle (maintained throughout the entire duration of the event). All individuals can look at one-another generating greater trust.

Brief Round of Introduction

Self-introduction using the following questions:

- name and surname
- place of origin
- current educational and/or professional situation

These questions should be written, so as all participants can have a visual reference and the cards with this information should be placed in the middle of the circle. Most youngsters these days do not carry their own pens or pencils unless they are attending

class and take notes in a physical notebook, many who have the possibility take note with a laptop. Hence it would be important to consider what materials are needed to ensure everyone has the adequate elements. Here, if the budget allows, a good alternative could be to have a “souvenir” with purpose, such as pencils with seeds that the attendees can eventually take home and plant. Particularly youngsters pay a lot of attention to these details, and it can be a great way to ensure their engagement.

Depending on the group, a general timeframe for personal introduction can be established.

➤ **Introduction to the Event - 5-10 minutes:**

Welcome message and overview of the session, where participants will also be able to ask any doubts or questions regarding the focus group, processes, objectives and/or follow up. Here the main climate change related issue will also be presented.

An “Introduction Narrative” sheet should be created; this can be in a physical or in a digital (e.g. slides) format depending on the type of attendees and/or physical space available. The oral explanation should be accompanied by visual elements that can allow all attendees to follow and adequately understand the event, also considering the possibility to have the information in bilingual or multilingual formats if necessary.

ACTIVITY 1: EXPERIENCE SHARING SESSION

Estimated time: 25-30 minutes

Method: *Shared Experience*

Once the introduction section is over, and participants have been able to introduce themselves and get to know one-another a bit, the first activity to follow is an exchange of personal experiences around the topic at hand. As during the introduction to the event phase the main issue is presented (which can be comprised of sub-topics or derived challenges), participants are encouraged to provide their insights on this matter.

Introduction to Activity 1 (5 minutes approx.)

To foster the exchange, guiding questions can be created and set in writing (either in physical or digital format, following the same principles as in the introductory section). These can also help individuals focus on more specific aspects, and it can be useful to either share pens and papers, or a copy of a sheet with the questions to each participant so they can write down any ideas that come to their mind before, during or after they speak and before, during or after other members of the focus group share their experiences.

Development of Activity 1 (25-30 minutes)

Participants will take rounds and have time to share their personal experiences linked to the topic at hand, they may mix information from their city/country of origin and their experiences in the city/region where they currently live and which is the subject and focus of the activity. It is important that all participants have time to share their experiences and moderators have an important role to keep track of time. Once individual views have been expressed, an open discussion to “connect the dots” and find a comprehensive common overview of the situation is established. There should be at least 5 minutes at the end to coordinate a joint approach and have a shared understanding of the problem being analysed, with the input from all participants.

Facilitators need to promote openness and respect from all individuals, and the objective is to establish a unified view on the situation at the end of this first activity.

This will be the basis of the remaining activities, which is why it is highly relevant that during this first activity all members can contribute and provide their input, so the final overview truly represents the sum of the individual perceptions, experiences, and approaches.

ACTIVITY 2: CO-CREATION OF SOFT ADAPTATION MEASURES

Estimated time: 50 minutes

Method: *Think, Pair and Share*

After the initial experience-sharing and taking the common understanding of the problem as the baseline information for this second phase, participants will be guided through a sequence of steps to co-create potential solutions. The placement of each person partaking in this activity should be in a circle or semicircle, and they can remain in the same place as during activity 1 or they may choose to move, always remaining in a round setting where all participants can see one another.

Introduction to Activity 2 (5 minutes approx.)

Facilitators will begin this second phase by explaining the framework of climate change adaptation, which should include the difference between **SOFT** and **HARD** adaptation measures (with examples). While carrying out this oral presentation, the moderator should distribute an example sheet with specific actions, policies and strategies that have already been implemented within the same region or elsewhere. Participants should have at least 2-3 minutes to read, comprehend and ask any questions they may have.

Execution of Activity 2 (35-40 minutes)

Once participants have understood the adaptation measures, the *Think, pair and share* method will be explained, with the sequential steps that will be followed. In this case, there will be an initial individual phase when each participant will ponder potential measures to propose, followed by a pair phase in which everyone will be sharing their views with another participant, thus forming pairs, and finally each pair will be explaining their views to the group and an overall co-creation process will be developed based on the different proposals.

Moderators should emphasize the relevance in identifying, prioritizing, and discussing the implications of each adaptation measure to address the impacts of climate change. The explanation sheet that was used in activity 1 can also be helpful and a guidance, although facilitators may choose to avoid introducing that sheet at this stage to avoid participants having any baseline idea. This will depend on the effect that is intended, both being valid courses of action.

During activity 2 the sequence will be:

- Individual Reflection Activity (5 minutes): participants will work individually, writing on blank paper / using examples if necessary.
- Prioritization of the adaptation measures considered most useful (3-5 minutes)
- Pair Discussion (10 minutes)
- General Discussion (15 minutes): This aims to identify one or more crucial adaptation measures to address the impacts of climate change for multicultural communities. At this stage, the facilitator will ask the pairs to a physical support (it may be post-its, a blank canvas, or other formats).
- Final selection of adaptation measures (5 minutes): participants will then mark with checkmarks on a maximum of two most agreed-upon concepts.
- Identification of the most agreed-upon adaptation measure (5-10 minutes), based on the individual selection. There should be a final group discussion so that consensus is reached.

Note: youngsters (it started with Millennials but Zentennials, Alpha, etc. followed) are the most sensitive cohort to the environmental choices and generation of waste, therefore take this into account to ensure the paper, post-its, and any other materials used are aligned with the expectations of the target audience. In some instances, the participants may not find coherent that much waste is generated only to carry out the activities, thus lowering the credibility of the focus group and whether there will be a real impact of their actions.

COFFEE BREAK (10 min)

Facilitators should be aware that during coffee breaks it is very common to see participants continuing the discussion. It is important to allow this process to continue in an informal setting, and during or after the coffee break to enable the selection to be reviewed if needed. The abovementioned note also applies here. Options such as biodegradable cups, having water fountains so individuals can refill their own bottle, etc. are much important to show consistency.

Regarding the objective of the activity, in the event the group did not reach consensus by the time the coffee break arrives, it is also valid to enable the discussion to continue during the refreshment as for some individuals this can be a better option to allow discussions to reach consensus.

Moderators should be aware of this and consider the most important objective is not when the agreement and final list of most-agreed upon adaptation measures is finalized, but to have this selection ready to begin the next activity. Hence, it can be during the coffee break that the last threads of the discussion are addressed and prior to starting the next activity, the list is finalized.

ACTIVITY 3: CO-EVALUATION OF ENGAGEMENT METHODOLOGIES

Estimated time: 60 minutes

Method(s): *1-2-4-All + How (simplified)*

Introduction to Activity 3 (3 minutes approximately)

Following the first two activities, the facilitator explains the method to be applied, emphasizing that participants will identify, prioritize, and discuss engagement methodologies related to the selected soft adaptation solution. Participants should be reminded to evaluate the options based on their preferences.

Activity 3.1: Individual Reflection (7 minutes approximately)

Here the activity is usually developed by writing on paper but explore the possibility to allow individuals to write on their own digital devices to be explored if the target audience is against using paper as it would generate waste.

Based on the previously selected soft adaptation solution, participants will note down individually ways in which they would like to be involved.

Activity 3.2: Prioritization of Methodologies Based on the Cards or Emergent Input (5 minutes approximately)

The facilitator has identified and separated a total of 5 cards (from 1 or 2 categories when the solution is intermediate) based on the previously selected soft adaptation solution (from Activity 2.2). The facilitator distributes the 5 cards (which have been previously explained to the participants), ensuring that each participant reads and understands the set of cards. Any questions or clarifications will be addressed at this stage. Participants will then need to select one methodology from the 5 proposed that they believe their target group would be most willing to engage with.

Activity 3.3: Pair Discussion and Prioritization (15 minutes approximately)

Method: "HOW"

The facilitator will divide participants into pairs. Each pair will discuss how they believe the preferred engagement methodology should be applied, as well as how it can be effectively implemented (using the "HOW" method), to delve deeper into the prioritized methodologies.

Facilitator Instructions: The facilitator should provide a detailed explanation of why this methodology is considered useful. It is essential that both participants actively engage in thinking about HOW the methodology can realistically be implemented by the City administration. This approach is intended to foster empathy and enhance the collective sense of community among the participants.

Activity 3.4: Discussion and Prioritization in Groups of Four (15 minutes approximately)

Method: "HOW"

Following the implementation of the pair discussion, each set of pairs will join another group of two, to share which were the methodologies they had previously chosen and either reinforce the selected one if they coincide, or discuss why one would be best, if possible agreeing on one final choice that represents the group of now four members. It is allowed for the group to jointly decide they wish to keep both options yet it should be thoroughly justified. For instance one applies better to one group of citizens while another would not be adequate for technical reasons and this implies there would be a need for a second option to be implemented to truly create an inclusive adaptation strategy.

Activity 3.5: Sharing Discussion (15 min minutes approximately)

Participants return to the plenary session to share their reflections, providing additional insights and feedback to other pairs. Each group of four will be able to explain their conclusions and all the ideas will be gathered in a single visual summary. This can either be created in a physical or digital manner, using tools such as a Miro board, again, catering to the needs and concerns of the participants. Knowing the cohort beforehand can contribute to the choice, however if this were not possible, it might be advisable to have both options at hand and allow participants to choose which one they feel most comfortable with.

CONCLUSIVE SESSION (15 minutes approximately)

Based on the final sharing discussion of Activity 3, the facilitator summarizes the outcomes of the session and explains the next steps for participants and how this information may be used by decision-makers, scientists and other stakeholders involved. With young cohorts this is particularly important as they are a group of stakeholders with high interest and relatively high power, wishing to be informed, are sceptical and have a lower trust towards institutions, having been involved in activism from a young age with initiatives such as Fridays for Future.

To complete the session, it would be advisable to have a feedback survey prepared so participants can provide their insights on the whole experience. This can have a section related to the event per-se and another section with more general questions linked to their involvement in future citizen engagement initiatives, which would be their preferred methods of engagement, as well as any other relevant aspect. The survey can be in paperback format or online, the latter being preferred by many younger members of society and it would also be easier to analyze as the data will already be in a digital format.